

Studies on *N*-Substituted Salicylhydroxamic Acid as Metal-complexing Ligand: *N*-Phenylsalicylhydroxamic Acid

Nripendra Nath Ghosh and Aruna Bhattacharyya

Salicylhydroxamic acid has been shown by many workers¹ to be a complex-forming ligand and some of the observations are of analytical importance. In order to study the effect of the substituents as alkyl, aryl, etc. to the nitrogen atom on the properties of the ligand, *N*-phenylsalicylhydroxamic acid has been prepared in poor yields by following the general method described by Bamberger², starting materials being phenylhydroxylamine and salicyl chloride. The reagent was recrystallised from a mixture of light petroleum and ether. It is readily soluble in ethanol, acetone, ether, etc., sparingly soluble in water, and almost insoluble in light petroleum; m.p. 106-107°. It was also recovered from an aqueous solution as copper compound, which was decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid to furnish the reagent R H₂ (the reagent may be regarded as having two replaceable hydrogen atoms and so for simplicity may be written as R H₂), purified by crystallisation. (Found: C, 68.39; H, 4.82; N, 6.15. C₁₃H₁₁O₃N requires C, 68.13; H, 4.80; N, 6.11%).

The reagent reacts with Cu(II), yielding a precipitate of copper compound of almost the same yellowish green colour as in the cases of other acyl-*N*-phenylhydroxamic acids³, acyl groups having no phenolic (OH) group. So it may be suggested that the structure of copper compound in each case is of the same type and the structure of the copper-R H₂ complex may be represented as:

the phenolic (OH) groups remaining free. Moreover, when copper compound in acetone suspension is treated with a neutral ferric chloride solution, a reddish violet colour develops; this colour indicates presence of phenolic (OH) group, which is still free after the formation of the copper compound with the reagent.

pH-titrations of a number of metal salt solutions, viz., Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Be(II), Fe(III), Al(III), Cr(III), Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Th(IV), V(V), U(VI), Mo(VI), containing free mineral acid and an excess of R H₂ solution, were made with a standard KOH solution. Almost in all cases the respective complex compounds were precipitated and approximate

1. Musante, *Gazzetta*, 1948, 78, 536; Bhaduri and Ráy, *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 95; Xavier *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 20, 146; Bhaduri, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1956, 151, 109; Bhaduri *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1957, 154, 103; *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1958, 297, 73; 1960, 303, 117; Divekar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 309.

2. *Ber.*, 1910, 52, 1116.

3. Lutwick and Ryan, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1954, 32, 849; Armour and Ryan, *ibid.*, 1957, 35, 1454.

pH values, at which the complete precipitation appeared to take place, were found out. Some of these compounds exhibit colour at lower pH and form precipitates at higher pH, e.g., Fe(III) compound develops a deep violet colour at lower pH with the formation of a chocolate-red precipitate at higher pH value and U(VI), an orange-red colour at lower pH and a brown precipitate at higher pH.

Some of the compounds were isolated by controlling the pH at which complete precipitation appeared to take place and their compositions were determined by analyses. The magnetic properties of some of the compounds were also studied. These appear to be high-spin type of complexes, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound with composition.	Colour.	pH range for pptn.	% Nitrogen.		% Metal.		Magnetic moment. (B.M.)
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
Cu(RH) ₂	Yellowish green	3.0—3.5	5.44	5.39	12.27	12.24	1.98
Ni(RH) ₂	Pale green	4.5—5.0	5.77	5.44	11.55	11.40	3.20
Fe(RH) ₃	Chocolate-red	1.7—2.0	5.53	5.68	7.65	7.55	5.91
VO(OH)(RH) ₂	Violet-black	1.2—1.5	5.29	5.19	9.41	9.43	Dia.
(UO ₂) ₂ R(RH) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown	4.5—5.0	3.33	3.34	37.79	37.82	..

Further work with this reagent, particularly its use for analytical purposes and with *N*-alkyl-substituted salicylhydroxamic acids, is in progress.

The authors express their thanks to Sri R. N. Chakravorty for micro-estimations.

DEPARTMENT OF PURE CHEMISTRY (INORGANIC LABORATORY),
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9.

Received January 7, 1964.